

ON THE STUDY OF INDIRECT APPLICATION OF RADIOACTIVE NUCLEI IN ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY

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It has been shown that through indirect method of analysis by radioactive nuclei, elements of γ order of magnitude can be estimated with a fair degree of accuracy. In the present investigation the estimation of Ag and I₂ has been undertaken using I¹³¹ as a measuring indicator. The principle involved in such estimations is as follows: Excess of iodine (double or triple the theoretical equivalent amount of Ag) as KI containing I¹³¹ is added to unknown Ag in acid solution; the trace of AgI is completely precipitated and is carried along with zirconium phosphate. From the loss in activity of I¹³¹ in the filtrate, the amount of Ag present can be calculated. With a known amount of Ag, unknown iodide can also be estimated under the same condition. It has been found that even one microgram (10^{-6} g.) of Ag can be estimated with statistical accuracy ($\pm 2\%$) within half an hour. Zirconium phosphate has been found a faithful carrier of AgI. It carries AgI even beyond the solubility limit. It appears that by the use of a suitable carrier a much lower limit than that reached by radiometric titration is always achieved.

As an extension to our study on indirect radiochemical estimation, the determination of weakly basic elements by allowing hydrolysis to completion with IO₃⁻--I⁻ mixture, was taken up. Aluminium up to the limit of 40 γ (40×10^{-6} g.) has thus been estimated with a fair degree of accuracy within 2 hours. Possible application of this principle to routine chemical analysis has also been discussed.

Most of the radiochemical estimations can be classified under two main heads, namely, either by process of activation in accelerators or reactors or by indirect applications of radioactive indicators. Though the first procedure is very sensitive in most of the cases, and in favourable circumstances even up to 10^{-12} g. of elements can be estimated, it is not always possible to have a reactor beside and conduct day to day analysis; so the second procedure of indirect radiochemical analysis also plays an important role in our every day laboratory work. Specially during the last few years, chemical analysis by radiometric titrations (Alimarin, "International Conference on Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy", 1955, 15, p. 60) has become popular and is finding extensive applications. It is going to replace the earlier method of indirect estimation by precipitating a fraction of the element with its radioactive isotope under investigation and measuring the loss in activity. In spite of various advantages, sensitivity and limit of analysis by radiometric titration are conditioned by the solubility of the compound precipitated. It was Sue (*Buil. soc. chim.*, 1946, v, 15, 103) who first attempted to overcome the solubility factor by carrying the invisible precipitate formed by a scavenger.

In his attempt to estimate silver, he took some known amount of KI and impregnated it with I¹³¹; he then added the micro amount of the silver salt to be estimated and carried this small amount of AgI precipitate by addition of Fe(OH)₃, prepared by addition of NaOH to FeCl₃ solution. He found that carrying was in most of the cases 98% up to the extent of 10^{-5} g. of silver, and beyond it there was incomplete carrying of AgI. (Even with 10 μ g. he got a negative error of about 10% in some cases). From

such considerations it seems that use of any scavenger may not lead us to counter-balance the solubility and other sources of errors associated with the estimation of micro amounts.

The main object of the present investigation is to find out a reagent that can coprecipitate AgI whereby a better degree of accuracy in much lower concentration in case of Ag and I can be achieved. Of the common substances, insoluble in acids with tolerable surface adsorption, zirconium phosphate, barium sulphate etc. come to mind. In the present investigation, zirconium phosphate has been used as a carrier of ultramicro quantities of AgI. It has been found to behave as a faithful carrier of AgI and high precision in the estimation of Ag and I in ultramicro quantities can be arrived at. The principle involved in such estimations is as follows: Excess of iodine (double or triple the theoretical equivalent amount of Ag) as KI containing I^{131} is added to unknown Ag in acid solution; the trace of AgI is completely precipitated and carried along with zirconium phosphate. From the loss in activity of I^{131} in the filtrate, the amount of Ag present can be calculated. In case we take a known amount of Ag, an unknown iodide can also be estimated under the same conditions.

The second objective of our study is to extend and apply I^{131} in the determination of weakly basic elements by allowing hydrolysis to completion with KIO_3 -KI mixture.

It is well known that the salt of a weakly basic element undergoes hydrolysis. If the hydrogen ion formed is progressively removed by some mechanism then in favourable circumstances hydrolysis becomes perfectly complete. Removal of the hydrogen ion in the present investigation has been carried out by the well-known iodate-iodide reaction.

The iodine liberated can be distilled and collected in alkaline sodium sulphite (or better in $N/10$ -NaOH) and estimated in case of large quantities by isotopic dilution and in case of small quantities, by adding a known amount of Ag and carrying it along with zirconium phosphate. Aluminium in potash alum has been taken as a representative of weakly basic elements.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents $AgNO_3$, KI, potash alum, KIO_3 , Na_2SO_3 , Na_2CO_3 and NaH_2PO_4 were all of G. R. E. Merck quality. The carrier-free I^{131} as supplied by Messers Philips Roxane was used. Zirconium nitrate of BDH (L.R.) was treated several times with perchloric acid and it was finally tested and found free from chloride and nitrate. It was kept in acid solution. Description of a typical experiment as given below will clarify the procedure adopted.

Estimation of Ag and I.—Ag as $AgNO_3$ of the order of a few micrograms was taken in a beaker. To the solution about three times the amount of iodine required by the equation

was added. Previous to this addition carrier-free I^{131} and I^{127} were thoroughly mixed; zirconium (~ 1 mg.) perchlorate was added; the solution as a whole was about $0.1N$ in

acidity. To this solution sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution was added in slight excess and the mixture was warmed for a few minutes till coagulation was complete. Zirconium phosphate together with coprecipitated AgI was then filtered through a naphthalene bed, and from the activity remaining in the filtrate, the amount of I_2 or Ag, as the case may be, was estimated. In most of the cases the measurements were done with a liquid counter under standard conditions. The volume in case of γ order of magnitude was not allowed to exceed 20 c.c. during the time of precipitation, and it was found that washing with 15 c.c. of water was sufficient to remove the excess iodide. In half an hour the whole operation including the activity measurements can be completed. Previous to the actual estimation, a study was made on the adsorption of I^{131} on zirconium phosphate (vide Table I). In case of estimation of Ag (vide Table II), a known amount of KI was added as mentioned above, and in case of unknown I_2 (vide Table III), a known quantity of Ag was added. The data are recorded in a tabular form.

Estimation of Aluminium.—Potash alum was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (dil.) in such volume that the concentration of the latter did not go below 0.2N. Aluminium in solution was analysed by oxine method according to Knowles (*J. Res., NBS, 1935, 15, 87*). The concentration of free acid was known from the known amount of acid added; this was also confirmed by determining free acid in presence of aluminium by the known method by titrating free acid with alkali in presence of excess $Na_2C_2O_4$. Purity of the alum was further tested by determining aluminium sulphate ratio. This was taken for a stock solution.

TABLE I

Adsorption of varying quantities of iodide on different amounts of zirconium phosphate.

No	Zr taken.	Vol. of precipitating medium.	I_2 taken in $\mu\text{g.}$ (10^{-6} g.)	% I adsorbed.
1.	2.5 mg.	30 c.c.	0.00 (without carrier)	87
2.	2.5	30	7.78	12
3.	2.5	30	23.34	0
4.	2.5	30	389.00	0
5.	1.0	30	7.78	8
6.	1.0	30	11.67	0
7.	1.0	30	15.50	0
8.	1.0	30	23.34	0
9.	0.5	15	3.89	20
10.	0.5	15	7.78	0
11.	0.5	15	7.78	0

TABLE II
Estimation of Ag.

No.	Experimental condition.	Silver in μg (10^{-6} g.).		Standard deviation in activity measurement.
		Taken.	Found.	
1.	6 mg. of Zr in 200 c.c.	187.6	189.0	$\pm 2\%$
2.	"	3.53	3.50	± 1.8
3.	"	3.53	3.63	± 3.4
4.	1 mg of Zr in 40 c.c.	172	170	± 2.0
5.	"	22.75	22.95	± 2.0
6.	"	32.78	32.18	± 2.2
7.	"	11.38	11.30	± 2.0
8.	"	9.00	9.08	± 1.8
9.	"	3.682	3.555	± 3.4
10.	0.5 mg Zr in 15 c.c.	1.67	1.658	± 1.5
11.	"	1.67	1.658	± 1.5
12.	"	1.67	1.660	± 1.5
13.	"	1.67	1.680	± 1.5
14.	"	1.67	1.650	± 1.5
15.	"	0.835	0.844	± 1.5
16.	"	0.835	0.826	± 1.5

The error is always within statistical fluctuation as shown above.

TABLE III
Estimation of iodine.

No.	Experimental condition	Iodine in ($\mu\mu\text{g} \times 10^{-6}$ g.).		Standard deviation in activity measurement.
		Taken.	Found.	
1.	1 mg of Zr in 30 c.c.	389.0	401.0	$\pm 2.2\%$
2.	"	399.0	395.0	± 2.2
3.	"	77.8	77.03	± 2.0
4.	"	38.9	38.10	± 2.0
5.	"	38.9	38.73	± 2.0
6.	"	15.56	15.53	± 1.8
7.	"	15.56	16.11	± 2.0
8.	6 mg. of Zr in 200 c.c.			
	"	778	794	± 2.5
9.	"	778	777	± 1.5
10.	"	23.34	23.48	± 2.0
11.	"	15.56	15.15	± 2.5
12.	0.5 mg. of Zr in 15 c.c.			
	"	7.78	7.90	± 2.0
13.	"	7.78	7.839	± 2.0
14.	"	7.78	7.839	± 2.0
15.	"	7.78	7.88	± 2.0
16.	"	7.78	7.80	± 2.0

Error as shown above is always within statistical fluctuation.

An aliquot portion of the stock solution containing about 23 mg. of aluminium was taken in an one-litre round bottomed flask fitted with a standard glass joint. Volume was made about 300 c.c. KI (— 5 g.) and KIO₃ (— 5 g.) were added and the flask was fitted to a delivery system including a condensing arrangement. On boiling, iodine was liberated with progressive hydrolysis and collected in a conical flask containing a solution of sodium sulphite or caustic soda, and cooled by ice to avoid escape of any iodine. In the case of estimating iodine by titrating against hypo, iodine was collected in a concentrated solution of potassium iodide, free from iodine. In case of micro-estimations, iodate-iodide was first added to water and two thirds volume distilled to drive out any free iodine which might be present in iodate or iodide. Double distilled water was all along used. The precision of the arrangement was tested by adding a known amount of sulphuric acid and estimating the iodine distilled. Aluminium was estimated by titrating iodine against hypo and also as AgI gravimetrically. To simplify the procedure of gravimetric estimation, iodine collected was labelled with I¹³¹ and estimation was done by isotopic dilution. In case of trace of aluminium, indirect procedure, as described above, was adopted.

TABLE IV

Estimation of aluminium by classical chemical methods.

No.	Aluminium (in mg.)		Amount of IO ₃ ⁻ and I ⁻ used in 300 c.c.	No.	Aluminium (in mg.)		Amount of IO ₃ ⁻ and I ⁻ used in 300 c.c.	Z	Aluminium (in mg.)		Amount of IO ₃ ⁻ and I ⁻ used in 300 c.c.
	Taken.	Found.			Taken.	Found.			Taken.	Found.	
1.	0.4674	0.4680(v)*	1g. KI 1g. KIO ₃	7.	23.37	23.71(v)*	5g. K ⁺ 10g. KIO ₃	12.	116.8	117.0(v)*	5g. KI 10g. KIO ₃
2.	0.4674	0.4723(v)*	Do	8.	23.37	23.57(v)*	Do	13.	116.8	116.95(v)*	Do
3.	2.337	2.344(v)*	1g. KI 2g. KIO ₃	9.	70.11	69.10(v)*	„	14.	4.674	4.657(G)*	1g. KI 2g. KIO ₃
4.	2.337	2.344(v)*	1g. KI 1g. KIO ₃	10.	116.80	115.2(v)*	„	15.	4.674	4.614(G)*	Do
5.	4.674	4.647(v)*	1g. KI 2g. KIO ₃	11.	116.80	116.1(v)*	„	16.	23.370	23.420(G)*	5g. KI 10g. KIO ₃
6.	4.674	4.672(v)*	Do					17.	23.370	23.145*(G)	Do

v*—Iodine was collected in a solution of iodine-free iodide (10 g.) in a conical flask cooled in ice. Glass wool on the mouth of the flask was used as a preventive measure. Two thirds of the volume was distilled and titrated against hypo.

G*—Iodine was absorbed in 0.4 g. of sodium sulphite and 0.1 g. of sodium carbonate and estimated gravimetrically as AgI.

TABLE V

Estimation of aluminium by the use of I¹³¹

No.	Aluminium (mg.) Taken.	Aluminium (mg.) Found.	Amount of IO ₃ ⁻ and I ⁻ used in 300 c.c.	No.	Aluminium (mg.) Taken.	Aluminium (mg.) Found.	Amount of IO ₃ ⁻ and I ⁻ used in 300 c.c.
1.	3.2116	3.136(D)* ±2.5%	0.5 g. KI 0.5 g. KIO ₃	6.	0.13764	0.1405(R)* ±2.3%	0.5 g. KI 0.5 g. KIO ₃
2.	4.588	4.506(D)* ±2.3%	Do	7.	0.18352	0.1870(R)* ±2.2%	Do
3.	0.04588	0.04543(R)* ±2.2%	..	8.	0.22440	0.2297(R)* ±2.3%	..
4.	0.04588	0.4544(R)* ±2.2%	..	9.	0.4588	0.4685(R)* ±2.3%	..
5.	0.09176	0.09045(R)* ±2.0%	..	10.	1.3764	1.3739(R)* ±2.2%	..

D*—Iodine was absorbed in 0.4 g. of sodium sulphite and 0.1 g. of sodium carbonate; I¹³¹ was added, thoroughly mixed and precipitated as CuI after neutralisation and mounted on a counting tray and estimated by isotopic dilution.

R*—Iodine was collected in sodium sulphite and sodium carbonate and slowly neutralised. Nearly one third equivalent of known silver was added and silver iodide was carried by zirconium phosphate following the same procedure as described in our experiment (by radiometric estimation).

DISCUSSION

The data on the estimation of Ag (Table II) show that very small quantities of Ag, even 10⁻⁶ g., can be estimated with a fair degree of accuracy within a very short time. The limit can be further extended beyond even a microgram if we can either make correction for surface adsorption of iodide ion at such low concentrations on Zr phosphate or overcome the adsorption factor by adding still lower quantities of Zr. But in such cases conditions, volume, etc. should also be changed.

One of the interesting aspects of the use of zirconium phosphate is that AgI is coprecipitated even beyond its solubility limit. Zirconium phosphate should not therefore be treated as a simple collector of invisible precipitate, but it is actually a coprecipitating agent; whereas Fe(OH)₃, as used by SHE, seems to be a collector; we have also found that it has got its limitations depending upon the iodine ion concentration in the solution. We are not yet certain why zirconium phosphate is such a faithful carrier of AgI, but we are hopeful that use of a carrier, which does not interfere with the excess of the constituents, will always lead us to a lower limit of estimation. The principle promises a better degree of accuracy than that can be achieved by estimating an element by radiometric titration and other indirect procedures. I¹³¹ was chosen as a preliminary start because of its popular use everywhere and its applications in the field of studies other than the insoluble iodides. Tables IV and V show that iodometric estimation of aluminium is a very convenient method. From general volumetric point of view, we are to take recourse to the

most popular hypo titration which is very accurate and very rapid. In case of gravimetric estimation, silver iodide is about twenty-six times the weight of aluminium taken; so the factor is very favourable for micro-determination of aluminium in the gravimetric way. In case of beryllium, equivalent amount of silver iodide will be forty-seven times the weight of beryllium. It is therefore very tempting for micro-chemists to run after this procedure. Question naturally arises whether we can apply this method to our day to day routine chemical analysis. The answer depends on the question of estimation of free acid by depressing the hydrolysis of weak bases in question or by some other means as has been done in the case of aluminium. It will form a subject matter of a separate study, specially in case of micro-determination.

It should be further noted that in case of high activity handling this method of determining weak bases will be very useful in a general chemical laboratory. It is of general interest whether this type of estimation will be of use to industry where the cost of reagents is also taken into account. We are quite confident that iodide and iodate can be used once and once again. Even the small quantity of zirconium, which has been used as carrier of AgI in estimating trace quantities of aluminium, can also be recovered and used again; the method is very simple and does not take more than two hours. Table IV describing the results of indirect radiochemical analysis will show that we did not go beyond 4×10^{-5} g. aluminium (40μ g.). It has been found by us that iodine liberated below this concentration of aluminium is rather high; many causes may be attributed to this high result. Our study in this aspect is still incomplete.

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